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Anomalous veins of the face and neck: an anatomical study with clinical implications

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Abstract

Background: The retromandibular vein normally divides into anterior and posterior divisions at the lower part of the parotid gland. The anterior division of the retromandibular vein unites with the facial vein to form the internal jugular vein, while the posterior division joins the posterior auricular vein, to form the external jugular vein. The posterior auricular vein may sometimes exhibit variations. The present research study, reports a lower division of the retromandibular vein and the absence of posterior auricular vein, and discusses its clinical implications.

Objective: To study a case of anomalous formation of external jugular vein, in which the posterior auricular vein was absent and did not contribute to the formation of external jugular vein.

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Material and methods: We observed the drainage pattern of the posterior auricular vein on both sides of 20 human cadavers (n=40). Any anomaly pertaining to the posterior auricular vein was observed.

Results: We observed the absence of posterior auricular vein on both sides of a 58 year male cadaver. On both sides, the retromandibular vein divided into an anterior and posterior divisions, 1.5 cm below the lower border of the parotid gland. The posterior auricular vein was absent. The posterior division of the retromandibular vein continued as the external jugular vein, and no other associated venous anomalies were observed.

Conclusion: Knowledge of venous anomalies may be important for academic interest and beneficial for facial surgeons and radiologists performing angiographic studies.

Key words: Posterior auricular, retromandibular, external jugular, face, vein, anomaly, variations.

Introduction

The retromandibular vein (RMV) is formed inside the parotid gland, by the union of the superficial temporal and the maxillary veins [1,2]. The RMV divides at the lower part of the parotid gland into an anterior and posterior division [1,2]. Both the divisions emerge from the

lower part of the gland, the anterior division of which, joins the facial vein (FV) at the lower border of the mandible, to form the common facial vein which drains into the internal jugular vein (IJV). The posterior auricular vein (PAV) arises from the parieto-occipital network and descends below the auricle to join the posterior division of the RMV to form the EJV [1]. EJV is commonly used for cannulation to conduct diagnostic procedures or intravenous therapies [3]. Vascular anomalies pertaining to the EJV as such are very rare and there is also paucity of literature on the absence of PAV [4]. The topographical anatomy of the neck and the FV is important for operating surgeons and radiologists interpreting sonographic investigations. While designing the posterior auricular flap for reconstructive surgeries, pre-operative planning is essential and the anomalies pertaining to PAV may be kept in mind [5]. The increase in stent grafting procedures for treating neurovascular diseases, also requires a thorough knowledge of the vascular anatomy of the neck region. The present study, describes an unusual case of the RMV dividing much below its usual position i.e at a distance of 1.5 below lower border of parotid gland and the absence of PAV. There are many research reports on the facial vein and EJV anomalies, but in the present case, a lower division of RMV with absence of PAV, is a rare entity, which may be important for academic and clinical purpose.

Materials and Methods

We observed the PAV on both sides of 20 formalin fixed cadavers (n= 40). The abnormalities pertaining to the PAV

were studied in detail in these twenty cadavers. The specimen was studied in detail and photographed (Figure.1).

Figure (1): Demonstrates absence of the posterior auricular vein from its usual position: P (Parotid gland), **Fv** (Facial vein), **Pa** (The usual position of the posterior auricular vein, it is absent in this case), **RV** (Retromandibular vein), **Ijv** (Internal jugular vein) **Sm** (Sternocleidomastoid muscle), **EJv** (External jugular vein) **SCv** (Subclavian vein).

Results

Out of 40 cases studied, the anomalous venous pattern PAV was noted on both sides of a 58 year male cadaver (5%). The FV traversed back from the lower border of the angle of the mandible. The RMV divided into anterior and posterior branches 1.5 cms below the lower border of the parotid gland. The PAV was characteristically absent. The EJV which usually joins the posterior division of the RMV was not observed, rather the EJV was formed as a continuation of the posterior division of the RMV. No other venous anomalies were observed.

Discussion

There are research reports on the FV uniting with the RMV in the parotid gland itself [6] but the present anomaly of the RMV dividing into anterior and posterior divisions, 1.5 cm below the parotid gland, is a rare finding. A recent research study, had reported the absence of anterior division of RMV, with the facial vein continuing as the IJV [7]. In the present case, we observed the posterior division of the RMV continuing as EJV, with the absence of PAV. An unusual finding of the PAV being absent also suggests that the other veins like occipital veins may be draining a larger part.

The facial vein has also been described to drain into the EJV [8]. In the present case, the facial vein joined the anterior division of the RMV 1.5 cm below the parotid gland, thereby resulting in a much smaller IJV. The IJV is usually accessed for diagnostic and therapeutic purpose and any anomaly of this kind, has to be borne in mind.

The variations in these veins could be explained in terms of the regression and retention of various parts of the veins as found in the rhesus monkey [8]. Absence of PAV, as observed in the present case, may puzzle the radiologists who might be exploring the PAV for investigative procedures. As anatomists we believe, that central venous catheterization may be difficult in the presence of such anomalies.

While designing flaps in the posterior auricular region, the anatomy of the PAV may be important [5]. In the absence of PAV, the flaps may not be possible because of less vascularity to the region. Surgeons have used

Prefabricated galeal flaps based on the superficial temporal or postauricular vessels for ear, cheek, mandible, and cranium reconstructions [9]. The use of retroauricular flaps for facial reconstructive surgeries has gained wide popularity. It has been found that the retroauricular flap provides normal color, texture, and thickness and thus is an optimal anatomic and aesthetic reconstruction with minimal donor-site morbidity [10]. Hence it is very important to know the variations of the superficial venous system in order to avoid damage to the fascia and ensure the survival of any flap [11].

The frequency of cerebral developmental venous anomalies, occurring in patients with cervicofacial vascular malformation is much higher than in general population [12]. Any venous anomalies may be explored for associated malformations.

Radiologists interpreting sonographic investigations may be puzzled with venous anomalies. Often during Doppler ultrasound procedures, a correct picture of the veins helps in proper interpretation and any deviation from the usual anatomy may cause erroneous interpretation.

Conclusion

The present study highlights the absence of PAV and reports the union of the anterior division of RMV with the facial vein, much below the usual lower border of the parotid gland, which is a rare finding. Knowledge of such venous anomalies may be helpful for academic, clinical and investigative procedures

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